

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

web presence

report

Oct. 2022 - Oct. 2023

This report highlights and summarizes visually data extracted from the E-RIHS website and social media over the last year (**October 1st, 2022 - October 2023, 1st**).

The report highlights strengths and weaknesses in the E-RIHS communication strategy and offers useful insight to identify the audience, monitor engagement and schedule targeted contents.

website
analytics

Audience

Users
3.8K

New users
3.7K

Views
10k

Event count
29k

page view **10K**
user engagement **7.9k**
session_start **6k**
first_visit **3.7K**
click **1K**
file_download **182**

97,4%

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

97,30%

Engagement

48,35%

Bounce Rate

The percentage of single-page sessions in which there was no interaction with the page. The bounced session has a duration of 0 seconds

homepage 62,54%

Channels

Behaviour

Average duration session

Views by Page

facebook
insights

Audience

↑ 24,8%

Gender

Age

Page new fans _ source

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

27,19%

Amplification Rate percentage

"It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks" (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

13,36%

Audience

Current audience

Potential audience

Estimated audience size ⓘ

38,600,000-45,400,000

People on Facebook and Instagram in Italy and 2 other filters selected

Post performance

↑ 208,9%

Posts

174

Likes

776

Reach

10.5K

↑ 522,5%

Page and profile visits

1513

↑ 299,2%

Post video reach

435

Top posts

<p>E-rihs.eu Apr 19, 07:10</p> <p>IPERION HS USERS MEETING #01 E-rihs.eu and Iperion HS present the first #UsersMeeting #01! 🎥📺 It's a chance to learn more about the TransNational Access (TNA) projects of access to IPERION HS facilities and archives FIXLAB, ARCHLAB</p> <p>17.65 % engagement rate</p>			
<p>E-rihs.eu Mar 14, 13:55</p> <p>Grant Opportunities New funding #opportunities are offered by the Institut Français and Université Franco-Italienne in the field of #HeritageScience. 📄 If you are a researcher, a student or a professor, you can read details and deadline at the link ht</p> <p>13.71 % engagement rate</p>			

twitter
analytics

Followers

Total
1063

New
86

↑ 8,09%

New followers

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

8,9%

Post performance

Amplification Rate percentage

"It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks"
(Avinash Kaushik, Google)

43,27%

Top post
Engagement rate
23,08%

E-RIHS EU
@ErihsEu

Promote ...

For weekly #HSAcademyDay we watch an overview of new #synchrotron light sources applied to #paleontological studies. With Douglas Galante, a scientist at LNLS/CNPEM, we discover an approach called #nanopaleometry! Watch the full Webinar bit.ly/3mT1Wik @CNPEM

Webinar #02 / February, 8th 2022

NEW SYNCHROTRON
LIGHT SOURCES AND
PALEONTOLOGICAL STUDIES
DOUGLAS GALANTE

HSAcademy

LinkedIn

analytics

Audience

Created with mapchart.net

↑ 61,66%

Unique visitors
515

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

160,85%

Post performance

Amplification Rate percentage

"It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks"
(Avinash Kaushik, Google)

87%

Channels

Top post

#jobopportunity

 E-RIHS 973 followers
2w •

Job Opportunity

The National Gallery has opened a job position for a **#Documentation** and **#DataManagement** Specialist (Conservation and Scientific).

If you are interested, please, apply now and feel free to spread the word!

- Departments: Conservation and Scientific, London
- Deadline to apply: 15th October
- Details and info: bit.ly/NatGallery_Job

#JobOpportunity #ResearchInfrastructure #HeritageScience

Heritage Science Online Forum

Heritage Research Hub

English Heritage

Fondation des sciences du patrimoine

ICCROM

Icon - The Institute of Conservation

■ Ph Credits: Wally Gobetz, <https://bit.ly/WallyGobetzPhotoFlickr> ■

YouTube

analytics

Audience

Jul-Oct
2023

Returning visitors **vs** Unique visitors
111 **552**

Audience Grow Rate percentage **50,43%**
It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

How viewers find the videos

Channels

Video performance

	Audience percentage viewed	11,9
	Shares	194

Amplification Rate percentage

"It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks" (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

56,55%

Top video

E-RIHS
EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

IPERION HS

HSAcademy

Current topics

VIVI TORNARI

PRINCIPLES OF HOLOGRAPHIC INTERFEROMETRY FOR NON-DESTRUCTIVE SUBSURFACE EXAMINATION

Moderated by emerging professionals

Lecture 02 / October, 20th 2022 at 3 pm Rome time

IPERION HS is a project funded
by the European Commission
under the IPERION

#CurrentTopicsHS Lecture 2/2022: Principles of holographic interferometry for subsurface examination

ERIHSEU
343 subscribers

Analytics

Edit video

11

Share

Download

326 views 11 months ago HS CurrentTopics lectures

Your top content in this period

Content	Views	Average view duration
#CurrentTopicsHS Lecture 2/2022: Principles of holographic interferometry for s... Oct 21, 2022	325	4:46 (11.9)
#CurrentTopicsHS Lecture 1/2022: From model to painting: edges and limits of ... Sep 16, 2022	303	5:15 (14.6)
#CurrentTopicsHS Lecture 8 (2023): X-Ray Imaging in cultural heritage Apr 21, 2023	241	5:27 (15.4)
IPERION HS How to successfully submit a proposal Nov 2, 2020	228	3:21 (47.9)
#HSAcademy webinar 9/2022: Olfactory heritage - preserving the smell of sites a... Nov 8, 2022	208	6:26 (18.9)
#CurrentTopicsHS Lecture 3/2022: Chromatographic analyses of molluskan purp... Nov 18, 2022	205	4:46 (12.7)
#HSAcademy webinar 4/2022: Hyperspectral and Multispectral Imaging in Herita... Apr 6, 2022	200	6:28 (10.4)
#CurrentTopicsHS Lecture 10/2023: Towards cathedrals of digital data and multi... Jun 26, 2023	182	3:48 (8.1)

YouTube

Hashtag

analytics

Monitoring hashtags helps us accelerate our growth on social media. We have identified two hashtags to amplify and maximize our impact on the social community:

#heritagescience

#e-rihs

At the moment E-RIHS use a free tracking tool for monitoring the hashtags, so these data are partial and not exhaustive. The analysis is related to the last three months (July-October 2023) and are mainly extracted from Twitter.

#heritagescience and #e-rihs

Mentions

Reach

Share of Voice

iperion hs: a relevant legacy

Overview

[Export to CSV](#)

	e-rihs	iperion hs
Total mentions ⓘ	43	43
Social media mentions ⓘ	3	26 ★
Non-Social media mentions ⓘ	40 ★	17
Positive mentions ⓘ	3% (1)	14% (6) ★
Negative mentions ⓘ	0% (0)	0% (0)
Social media reach ⓘ	4934	41K ★
Non-Social media reach ⓘ	114K ★	25K
Presence score ⓘ	5/100	6/100 ★
AVE ⓘ	\$ 9544 ★	\$ 4979
User generated content ⓘ	3	26 ★

Overview

[Export to CSV](#)

	e-rihs	heritagescience
Total mentions ⓘ	43 ★	34
Social media mentions ⓘ	3	33 ★
Non-Social media mentions ⓘ	40 ★	1
Positive mentions ⓘ	3% (1)	24% (8) ★
Negative mentions ⓘ	0% (0)	0% (0)
Social media reach ⓘ	4934	86K ★
Non-Social media reach ⓘ	114K ★	19
Presence score ⓘ	5/100 ★	3/100
AVE ⓘ	\$ 9544 ★	\$ 6545
User generated content ⓘ	3	32 ★

heritage science

e-rihs

The most influential

The most active

Top public profiles

Profile	Voice Share	Influence
HertSci_UK	40.2%	34 616
iperion_hs	24.6%	21 200
Scottish3D	9.5%	8200
lucianoor_m	4.9%	4200
ErihsEu	4.2%	3606

The most influential sites

The most popular mentions

Latest mentions

-
ErihsEu 2023-09-28 03:41
twitter.com 1
 on the next activities and the creation of E-RIHS ERIC! Check out our website <http://www.e-rihs.eu>
-
E-RIHS on LinkedIn: #usersmeeting 2023-10-05 22:45
[linkedin.com](https://www.linkedin.com)
 it's the first appointment of the joints event E-RIHS & JPI-CH for 2023 and the meeting will
-
Photoacoustic real-time monitoring 2023-10-12 01:52
[sciencedirect.com](https://www.sciencedirect.com)
 FIXLAB-1.gr at IESL-FORTH, Heraklion, belonging to the Greek E-RIHS.gr developed and supported pa...
-
Daniele Ferdani – University of B 2023-09-22 15:00
[unibo.it](https://www.unibo.it)
 involved as provider in the activities of the E-rihs.it mobile laboratories. He holds a Masters in
-
ERIHS EU 2023-10-12 01:21
[youtube.com](https://www.youtube.com)
 The 4th User meeting event, organized by HS Academy in collaboration with the Joint Programming L...

Comparing data

Mapping our audience

 Website

 Facebook

 LinkedIn

Summarizing our social presence

Posts/videos

174

271

168

51

Followers

898

1063

973

343

Impressions

10,5K

3,7K

42K

65,6K

Audience Grow rate percentage

27,2%

9%

160,9%

50,5%

Amplification rate percentage

13,4%

43,3%

87%

56,6%

E-RIHS national nodes

The analysis of the E-RIHS web presence will contain comparisons with previous reporting period starting from the next year.

For a few years, the E-RIHS website and social media have been not updated regularly for different reasons.

From the analysis of the IPERION HS social media and website (DOI: <https://zenodo.org/record/7382741>), which is a correlated EU project, we learnt that users are mainly interested in access calls, training and job opportunities, as the top posts and videos confirm.

The E-RIHS ERIC will start soon and its contents will be possibly more attractive for the heritage science community. In the meanwhile, E-RIHS communication is active jointly with IPERION HS and the ARCHE project.

We have set the following KPI for social media (DOI: <https://zenodo.org/record/7849261>):

Profile visits – followers – new followers – engagement – mentions – interactions – audience grow rate percentage – amplification rate percentage.

We will set quantitative goals once E-RIHS will be consolidated as an ERIC to monitor communication performances and improve our strategy on social media and website.

Report by Laura Benassi and Silvia Manconi - 2023

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